

Infinity and contradiction

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Abstract. This paper shows how the infinity of natural numbers can produce a real contradiction.

Keywords: infinity, contradiction, decimal number system, natural numbers, bijective applications, injective applications

1 Finite quantity of natural numbers

Theorem 1.1. *If we take a bijective application f between any set X and any set Y :*

$$\forall x \in X \exists! y \in Y : (x, y) \in f$$

$$\forall y \in Y \exists! x \in X : (x, y) \in f$$

and we want to construct from it an application h in which a precise number x of the set X is connected to a precise number y of the set Y :

$$h = \{ \dots (x, y) \dots \}$$

and for the application h the following conditions apply:

1. *is identical to the bijective application f except for the new pair (x, y) that is produced and therefore also for the two numbers a, b associated with x, y in the application f :*

$$f = \{ \dots (x, a), (b, y), \dots \}$$

2. *is injective between the set X and the set Y :*

$$\forall x_1, x_2 \in X : x_1 \neq x_2 \rightarrow h(x_1) \neq h(x_2)$$

3. *does not have within it numbers of the set Y different from those present in f*

we get as a result an application h that will involve altogether the same numbers of the application f .

Proof.

As stated in the property 1) by connecting the number x to the number y , the numbers a, b that were connected with them within the application f remain unpaired within the application h .

As stated in the property 2), the number b of the set X that has remained unpaired cannot be connected within the application h with numbers of the set Y that are already connected to numbers of the set X .

As stated in the property 1), the numbers of the set Y to which the numbers of the set X are already connected within the application h are all those present within the application f except the number a .

As stated in the property 3), the number b of the set X cannot be connected within the application h even with all the numbers of the set Y not present within the application f .

The only number of the set Y to which the number b of the set X can be connected within the application h is the number a , which has also remained unpaired, thus obtaining an application h which involves exactly all the numbers of the application f .

□

Theorem 1.2. *Given a generic application f , bijective between any set X and any set Y , any possible injective application h between these sets satisfies the two following conditions:*

1. *must necessarily be constructible from the application f*
2. *will involve altogether the same numbers of the application f .*

Proof. Any application h , injective between the set X and the set Y , is always obtainable from an application f , bijective between the same sets, as both take the same numbers of the set X and connects them to distinct numbers of the set Y . Therefore, to pass from the application f to the application h it will be sufficient to take the numbers of the set X , one at a time, and connect them not to the numbers of the set Y that the application f originally assigned to them but to the new ones that the application h assigns to them.

Given the generic application f :

$$f = \{(x_1, f_1), (x_2, f_2), (x_3, f_3), (x_4, f_4), \dots, (x_n, f_n), \dots\}$$

and the generic application h :

$$h = \{(x_1, h_1), (x_2, h_2), (x_3, h_3), (x_4, h_4), \dots, (x_n, h_n), \dots\}$$

we will have as first step the following application f_1 :

$$f_1 = \{(x_1, h_1), \dots, (x_n, f_n), \dots\}$$

as second step the following application f_2 :

$$f_2 = \{(x_1, h_1), (x_2, h_2), \dots, (x_n, f_n), \dots\}$$

as thirds step the following application f_3 :

$$f_3 = \{(x_1, h_1), (x_2, h_2), (x_3, h_3), \dots, (x_n, f_n), \dots\}$$

and so on.

To ensure that these steps lead to the application h is its property to assign always distinct numbers of the set Y to the numbers of the set X . In this way, any successive assignment will never interfere with the assignments made previously.

Since the first application f_1 is designed to satisfy the following conditions:

1. is identical to the bijective application f except for the new pair (x_1, h_1) that is produced
2. is injective between the set X and the set Y
3. does not have within it numbers of the set Y different from those present in f

leads us to conclude, thanks to theorem 1.1, that the application f_1 involves the same numbers of the application f and therefore is itself bijective.

Since each generic intermediate application f_i (with $i \in N$, $i \neq 1$, and N the set of natural numbers) is designed to satisfy the following conditions:

1. is identical to the application f_{i-1} except for the new pair (x_i, h_i) that is produced
2. is injective between the set X and the set Y
3. does not have within it numbers of the set Y different from those present in f_{i-1}

leads us to conclude, thanks to theorem 1.1, that if the application f_{i-1} involves the same numbers of the bijective application f and therefore is itself bijective, the same must apply to the application f_i .

So by applying the induction principle to the steps leading the application f to the application h we obtain that also the application h will have to involve the same numbers of the application f .

□

Theorem 1.3. *The set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ of non-zero natural numbers, constructed using the decimal number system, can only have a finite number of elements.*

Proof. First let's assume that the decimal numerical system is capable of representing every natural number, without any limit. This allows us to write the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ in the following way:

$$\mathbb{N}_{>0} = \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots\}$$

Let's now take the set P whose elements coincide with the even numbers of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ just defined:

$$P = \{2, 4, 6, 8, \dots\} \subset \mathbb{N}_{>0}$$

and the set A which is limited only to the even numbers present within the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$, and is therefore its proper subset:

$$A = \{2, 4, 6, 8, \dots\} \subset \mathbb{N}_{>0}$$

Let's now take the following application $f: \mathbb{N}_{>0} \rightarrow P$

$$f(2)=2$$

$$f(4)=4$$

$$f(6)=6$$

$$f(8)=8$$

...

that follows the rule:

$$f(2 \cdot n) = 2 \cdot n \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}_{>0}$$

Having considered the decimal numerical system capable of representing every natural number, without any limit, the application f will be valid for all the elements of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ that are even numbers, and therefore also for all the elements of its proper subset A , and for all the elements of the set P , none excluded.

This means that the application f is bijective between the set A and the

set P , and therefore it will be true that:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall a \in A \exists! p \in P : (a, p) \in f \\ \forall p \in P \exists! a \in A : (a, p) \in f \end{aligned}$$

And we can represent the application f in the following way:

$$f = \{(2, 2), (4, 4), (6, 6), (8, 8), \dots, (2 \cdot n, 2 \cdot n), \dots\}$$

with pairs that have as left element a different element of the set A and as right element a different element of the set P , and that taken together exhaust both the elements of one and the elements of the other.

At this point, due to the theorem 1.2, we can conclude that every application h , injective between the set A and set P , will involve all the numbers of the bijective application f found here, and therefore both all the numbers of the set A and also all the numbers of the set P .

This means that no bijective application between the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ and the set P will be possible. In fact, if such an application could exist, the even numbers of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ and therefore the numbers of the set A would inevitably be in injective correspondence with the numbers of the set P . But as we have just seen, this already implies that the numbers in the set A involve all the numbers in the set P . And so there will be no other numbers in the set P to which the odd numbers in the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ can be matched.

However, if we take the following application $k: \mathbb{N}_{>0} \rightarrow P$

$$\begin{aligned} k(1) &= 2 \\ k(2) &= 4 \\ k(3) &= 6 \\ k(4) &= 8 \\ &\dots \end{aligned}$$

that follows the rule::

$$k(n) = 2 \cdot n \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}_{>0}$$

and we make the hypothesis of a decimal numerical system capable of representing every natural number, without any limit, this application will be valid for all the elements of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ and for all the elements of the set P , none excluded. And so it will in fact be a bijective application between the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ and the set P , allowing us to write:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall n \in \mathbb{N}_{>0} \exists! p \in P : (n, p) \in k \\ \forall p \in P \exists! n \in \mathbb{N}_{>0} : (n, p) \in k \end{aligned}$$

Since such an application should not have been bijective, there is a contradiction. And since this contradiction occurs in an inevitably way starting from the hypothesis that the decimal numerical system is capable of representing every natural number, without any limit, we are forced to consider this hypothesis false.

This means that if we want to avoid this contradiction, there must be at least one natural number that cannot be represented by the decimal numerical system. Which number will limit those that can be represented by such a system to the only ones that precede it, which will therefore be finite. □

2 New prospects in mathematics

In the margin of this demonstration we can briefly mention that if the non-zero natural numbers are finite, the integer numbers that are the same with the addition of their opposites and zero must also be finite. Moreover, if we proceed in a completely specular way to what we have just seen, we can demonstrate that even the rational and irrational numbers that can be represented by the decimal numerical system must be finite.

Finally, applying the procedure adopted here also in the axiomatic set theory, we immediately come to the conclusion that natural numbers, having to be finite, cannot be constructed with Peano axioms.